

ENGLISH ARTICLE AND ITS ROLE IN TEXT GRAMMAR

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Annotation

The relevance of the study of the functions of English articles is connected not only with the need to know the system of functions of the most important operators of speech, but also with the needs of speech practice: articles top the list of the most frequently used units of English texts and are the source of most of the most common speech errors.

Key words

Articles, meanings, function, semantic function, definite, indefinite, linguistic, aspects.

The article is a functional word, one of the signs of nouns, but among the functional words the article occupies a special place. A distinctive feature of the articles is that they are words of pronominal origin: the definite article “the” came from the word that meant this, and the indefinite - from the word that meant one, some. Studies of the formation of articles have shown that the indefinite article would never have developed from “an” if it did not have the meaning of “an” indefinite pronoun - a simple quantitative value was still not enough for this.

As Shteling D.A. writes [1], even the original meanings of articles are abstract: after all, the pronoun is “the most common word”. In articles, the grammatical meaning is even greater than in prepositions and conjunctions, it prevails over the lexical one. Even if the meaning and function of the preposition is often established only from the semantic structure of the sentence (to sit by the window; the door was opened by John), then this applies to articles to an even greater extent.

Chernyshov M.Yu. [2] classifies some of the 205 functions as follows:

1. Morphological functions.
2. Syntactic functions. This class includes the function of highlighting a noun or a nominal phrase in a sentence.
3. Semantic functions: a) the function of transferring specific concepts; b) the function of understanding the speech construction “Art + N” in this phraseological context;

4. Semantic-pragmatic functions: according to a number of grammarians, the definite article performs a referential function; other authors also name this function, but refer it to the set of logical functions of the article.

5. Communicative-pragmatic functions. Their set includes, for example, a communicative function, understood as a function of introducing new information and forming a "focus of communication" (ie, "rhyme" of an utterance).

6. Logic functions. This class includes the function of expressing the values of the definiteness/indefiniteness of a noun; the function of expressing particular or general in a noun; the function of indicating its computability and in computability; anaphoric function; and the function of the indefinite article, "determining the method of aspectization."

When the definite article highlights a class of objects, it is not a quantitative moment that comes to the fore, but the meaning of a qualitative originality, uniqueness, as unique in reality, individual, unique, specific precisely for this substance, incomparable with anything, distinguishing from all other objects. Some authors combine these meanings of the definite article under a common sign of identification. The meaning of identification is the main one for this article. It is used when re-nominating an object, if there is a restrictive definition in the context that distinguishes the object from similar ones, when designating one-of-a-kind objects, it can be due to the very situation of communication. Identification is observed with the generalizing meaning of the definite article.

The indefinite article characterizes the object with the name of which it is associated as one of the representatives, any of the representatives of a particular class of objects. The indefinite article is a classifying article: "I saw a tree in the distance."

All linguists recognize the presence of definite and indefinite articles as indicators of certainty, uncertainty. However, the question of the existence of the zero articles or the so-called significant absence of it is not clear. But one thing is clear that the use of the zero articles has become more and more common. The article is interpreted as a service part of speech, which includes two independent words: the definite article and the indefinite article. Some authors emphasize the zero articles, and the absence of the article is also considered significant.

It is worth saying that it is difficult to formulate clear rules for the use of definite and indefinite articles. Rules can only be general and approximate. The number of options is unlimited, so you should remember the basic meanings of words

and forms, in accordance with which they participate in various combinations of contexts, and accumulate these contexts in memory along with the accumulation of meaningful information.

References:

1. Barmina L.A., Verkhovskaya I.P. Practicum in English: Articles. - M., 2000.
2. Weikhman G.A. New in English grammar. - M., 1990.
3. Vinogradov V.A. Linguistic encyclopedic dictionary. Article. - M., 1990.
4. Ershova N.N. Some cases of using the zero article in modern English. - M., 2004.

